

Benchmarking Reveals Shared Biases in Sleep-Staging Algorithms and Points to Age-Aware Solutions

M. Bechny^{1,2}, A. Dei Rossi³, M. Metald², J. van der Meer⁴, M. Schmidt⁴, C. Bassetti⁴, A. Tzovara¹, F. Faraci², L. Fiorillo^{2,5}

¹University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland, ²SUPSI-MeDiTech, Lugano-Viganello, Switzerland, ³Università della Svizzera Italiana, Lugano-Viganello, Switzerland, ⁴Inselhospital, Universitätsspital Bern, Bern, Switzerland, ⁵Ente Ospedaliero Cantonale, Lugano, Switzerland

Type

Presentation type: Poster presentation

Please consider this abstract for the Asian Society of Sleep Medicine (ASSM) meeting to be held on Saturday and Sunday, September 6-7, 2025.: No

General data

Topic: Technology/Technical

Secondary topic: Other

Abstract text

Introduction: Deep learning (DL) algorithms (models) hold promise for automating the labor-intensive task of sleep-staging. Yet, clinical adoption remains limited due to inter-scorer variability, partly stemming from ambiguities in AASM guidelines¹, which constrains model performance and hinders translation. Debates over optimal DL architectures are further complicated by heterogeneous datasets and inconsistent validation protocols. While standardized benchmarking is key, it must be paired with subgroup-specific performance analysis. To address this, we trained state-of-the-art DL-models within a harmonized, large-scale benchmarking framework and evaluated them using a robust, distribution-aware approach to quantify systematic biases.

Materials and methods: We leveraged DL-models from the SLEEPYLAND² benchmarking platform (U-Sleep³, DeepResNet⁴, SleepTransformer⁵), pre-trained on over 27,000 harmonized PSGs from 17 public datasets using standardized pipelines to ensure comparability. These models were then evaluated on 6,633 out-of-distribution PSGs from the Bern Sleep-Wake Registry⁶, spanning ages 0-88 and diverse clinical conditions. To assess bias in individual sleep-scoring models, we applied a GAMLSS-based framework^{7,8} that quantifies the full distribution of both model performance metrics (e.g., macro- or stage-specific F1-score) and errors in prediction-derived clinical markers (e.g., sleep-stage durations, number of stage-transitions). This approach captures non-linear effects of age while adjusting for covariates such as gender, AHI, and PLMI, characterizing individual health status. Beyond mean trends, it quantifies variability and extremes, and enables formal testing of how these variables shape model behavior, offering a comprehensive view of clinically relevant, variable-driven biases.

Results: Despite architectural differences, all models showed similar average performance (macro-F1 \approx 0.75) and exhibited consistent bias patterns. Performance declined markedly at age extremes, especially in children, reflecting underrepresentation in training data and differences in AASM scoring rules. Non-linear age-related biases were observed across all performance metrics and prediction-derived clinical markers. Higher AHI and PLMI were associated with greater errors and variability, likely due to fragmented sleep and signal artifacts. Among stages, N1 remained the most challenging (F1 \approx 0.45), while REM and wake were the most reliable. All models consistently overestimated WASO, and consequently the number of awakenings, and underestimated N3 duration, with the strongest biases observed in younger and high-AHI subgroups. Notably, stage transitions were systematically undercounted, producing overly smoothed hypnograms, likely a result of loss functions used during DL-model optimization.

Conclusions: Our analysis shows that performance and marker biases in DL-based sleep-staging are consistent across architectures and primarily driven by demographic and clinical factors, rather than model design. These findings underscore the need for structured validation of algorithm behavior across real-world subgroups. Our GAMLSS-based framework supports this by quantifying full distributions of performance and marker errors, and identifying sources of systematic bias. Strong non-linear age effects, likely reflecting AASM scoring differences between pediatric and adult populations, suggest that future DL-models could benefit from incorporating age as their input. Additionally, training strategies such as targeted upsampling of underrepresented groups may help mitigate imbalance-driven bias. Given the consistency of bias patterns across models, future progress in automated sleep-staging should prioritize subgroup-aware mitigation strategies over further architectural innovation, to ensure fair and clinically reliable deployment.

Acknowledgments:

P-5-B-Open Science (2021-2024) TP80: SLEEPYLAND

1. <https://jcs.m.aasm.org/doi/10.5664/jcs.m.5176>
2. <https://github.com/biomedical-signal-processing/sleepyland>
3. [10.1038/s41746-021-00440-5](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-021-00440-5)
4. [10.1093/sleep/zsaa161](https://doi.org/10.1093/sleep/zsaa161)
5. [10.1109/TBME.2022.3147187](https://doi.org/10.1109/TBME.2022.3147187)
6. [10.3390/ctn8010014](https://doi.org/10.3390/ctn8010014)
7. [10.1109/SDS60720.2024.00045](https://doi.org/10.1109/SDS60720.2024.00045)
8. [10.21203/rs.3.rs-6278214/v1](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-6278214/v1)

General

1. I confirm that the abstract and that all information is correct: Yes

2. I confirm that the abstract constitutes consent to publication: Yes

3. I confirm that I submit this abstract on behalf of all authors.: Yes

I understand that the presenting author MUST register for the congress: Yes